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IMPACT OF CAPITAL STRUCTURE ON SHARE PRICE: A STUDY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SELECT INDIAN PUBLIC SECTOR BANKS

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ABSTRACT

Market Value of Share of a company is determined by various factors. Capital Structure is one of the variables which determine the market price of the share. In this study an attempt was made by using Multiple Regression model to see how for the Capital Structure of the firm has got an effect over the Market value of share. Debt to Total Assets, Equity to Total Assets, Gearing Ratio and Market price of share of eleven Indian public sector banks were taken for the study for five years from March 2013 to March 2017. The study witnessed the Impact of Capital Structure on Share price.

Keywords: Indian Public sector Banks, Share Prices, Gearing Ratio, Equity, Debts

JEL Classification: G10, G12, G13

Introduction

The share price of a firm is affected by various factors. Determination of share price is not an easy task. The share price movement is based on the firm's fundamentals (Key performance indicators of firm), Market efficiency, Macroeconomic Indicators (Gross Domestic Product, Oil Prices & Inflation etc) and Perception of the Investors. Several studies have proven that share price of firms are explained by its capital structure. In this study an attempt was made by using Multiple Regression model to see how for the Capital Structure of the firm has got an effect over the Market value of share. Debt to Total Assets, Equity to Total Assets, Gearing Ratio and Market price of share of eleven Indian public sector banks were taken for the study for five years from March 2013 to March 2017. The study witnessed the Impact of Capital Structure on Share price.

Review of Literature

John C. Groth, Ronald C. Anderson, (1997) studied the capital structure from the perspective of the managers. From their study they revealed several practical strategies to enhance the value of the firm through capital structure.

Raheel Safdar, Chen Yan, (2016) made an attempt to find the impact of cost of capital on the share price movement. From their study they revealed that the cost of capital is impacting the market value of share.

George Athanassakos, (2007) studied share price movement of companies adopting value based management. The result of the study revealed that firms which concentrate on Economic Value Addition will be able to increase its share price performance.

Cécile Carpentier, (2006) studied in the title "The valuation effects of long-term changes in capital structure". In the study the researcher tried to look after the impact of changes in the capital structure in the value of the firm

Athanasios G. Noulas, Georgios Genimakis, (2014) surveyed the CFO'S of Greek listed companies. From the survey they revealed how the CFO'S of Greek listed companies make decisions in terms of capital structure.

Research Methodology

The study relied upon the secondary data. Debt to Total Assets, Equity to Total Assets, Gearing Ratio and Market share price of eleven Indian public sector banks were taken for the study for five years from March 2013 to March 2017. Correlation and Regression are used in this study.

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis were framed for the study

H0: There is no impact of Equity to Total Asset on the share price

H0: There is no impact of Debt to Total Asset on the share price

H0: There is no impact of Gearing Ratio on the share price

Data Analysis

Table 1 :Correlations					
		equity/ta	debt/TA	GEARING RATIO	SHARE PRICE
equity/ta	Pearson Correlation	1	-.421**	-.605**	-.411**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001	.000	.002
	N	55	55	55	55
debt/TA	Pearson Correlation	-.421**	1	.701**	.428**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001		.000	.001
	N	55	55	55	55
GEARING RATIO	Pearson Correlation	-.605**	.701**	1	.545**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	55	55	55	55
SHARE PRICE	Pearson Correlation	-.411**	.428**	.545**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.001	.000	
	N	55	55	55	55
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).					
Source: Computed Data					

Inference

From the Table 1 it is observed that Equity to Total asset has a negative correlation of 41.1% with share price, Debt to Total asset has a positive correlation of 42.8% with share price and Gearing Ratio has a positive

correlation of 54.5% with share price. However the correlation alone is not enough to fulfill the objective of the study. The study proceeds further with regression analysis.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.980 ^a	.960	.957	.10804	.960	403.462	3	51	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), GEARING RATIO, equity/ta, debt/TA

Source: Computed Data

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14.128	3	4.709	403.462	.000 ^a
	Residual	.595	51	.012		
	Total	14.724	54			

a. Predictors: (Constant), GEARING RATIO, equity/ta, debt/TA

b. Dependent Variable: LOG SHARE PRICE

Source: Computed Data

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.251	.053		23.769	.000
	equity/ta	-143.762	9.907	-.513	-14.511	.000
	debt/TA	8.100	.787	.406	10.298	.000
	GEARING RATIO	.002	.000	.247	5.494	.000

a. Dependent Variable: LOG SHARE PRICE

Inference

Table 2:

The R² in the model is 0.960 which means that the independent variables Equity to Asset, Debt to Asset and Gearing Ratio can explain 96% of change in the dependent variable (MV). The adjusted R² demonstrates that 95.7% of the variances between dependent and independent variables in this model.

Table 3:

The model shows that the independent variables Equity to Asset, Debt to Asset and Gearing Ratio had the significant impact of this variable on dependent variable Market Value of Shares

Table 4:

With reference to the beta co-efficient and sig.value it is found that the independent variables Equity to Asset, Debt to Asset and Gearing Ratio show impact on dependent variable Market Value of Shares (MVS) significantly. The statistical tests applied in this case, also suggest there is a strong relationship between independent variables and dependent variable.

Conclusion

Based on the statistical analysis it is concluded that Capital Structure holds its impact on the market value of share and have a significant and positive relationship between Capital Structure and Market Value of Shares.

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